

CLOSING THE LOOP ON ABSORBENT HYGIENE PRODUCTS

O. Bolognani ⁽¹⁾, G. Landolfo ⁽¹⁾, G. Poliseo ⁽¹⁾, M. Somma ⁽¹⁾, M. Mattiello ⁽²⁾

1: FaterSMART Business Unit, Fater SpA, Via Alessandro Volta n. 10, Pescara, Italy.

2: Contarina, Via Vittorio Veneto, 6, Lovadina di Spresiano TV, Italy.

Abstract: Every year, 30 million tons of used Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHP), representing 3-4% of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW), end their life worldwide in landfills or incinerators. FaterSMART has developed and patented a breakthrough recycling solution that makes it possible to recycle this waste stream, turning it into high value applications, with tangible environmental benefits. The system, which today can showcase the first-in-the-world industrial scale facility up and running in Italy in partnership with Contarina SpA, allows to process and sterilize separately collected AHP waste, recovering the valuable materials it contains with high purity levels: polyolefin plastics, cellulose and superabsorbent polymer. With a continuous research activity that aims at reaching breakthroughs in every field, the next step through the H2020-BBI EMBRACED project is the further valorization of the secondary raw materials and of all the process by-products into high value bio-based materials and products, as a perfect example of Circular Economy.

Key words: AHP waste, Recycling, Secondary Raw Materials, Biorefinery, Bio-based materials and products

1. Introduction

Absorbent Hygiene Products (AHPs) have become essential everyday products to society and their use has increased substantially. As with every consumer product, also AHP's end up in solid waste after their use. Today, they represent approx. 3-4% of the total municipal solid waste and are considered a non-recyclable fraction, which is usually incinerated or land-filled. Over the past 20 years, there has been great progress by AHPs manufacturers to reduce the environmental impact of AHPs. For example, the average weight of baby diapers was reduced by around 50%. Yet, to meet society's needs for sustainable consumption, there is further innovation required. The unique FaterSMART recycling technology, already demonstrated at industrial scale (10,000 tons/year capacity), allows to turn this waste stream into high value applications, offering a highly innovative demonstrative example of implementation of the EU circular economy package.

2. Turning AHP waste into high value products

2.1. AHP waste separate collection

A pre-requisite for the implementation of AHP recycling is the set-up of separate collection services for this waste stream from households or other relevant producers (nursing homes, hospitals, day care centers), in order to secure a stable input flow to the recycling plant. As the EU moves towards its recycling targets, AHP waste has quickly risen to represent already up to 15-25% of the residual waste in some territories, where residual waste drops to 30% or less of all MSW produced. Indeed, such schemes are already implemented in many municipalities across the EU and a quick growing trend is observed, in particular in areas where collection frequencies for the residual waste are low (fortnightly or even lower) and Pay-As-You-Throw charging systems are in place. In Italy, for example, already 12 million inhabitants in over 800 municipalities are covered by AHP waste collection services, even where no recycling solution is yet in place.

2.2. The AHP waste recycling plant

The AHP waste recycling plant envisages an initial section for the unloading of the AHP waste coming from the separate collection and its stocking in a closed chamber to avoid unpleasant odors. The material is then transferred to an autoclave for the first phase of the treatment: sterilization. Within the autoclave, which operates in batch mode, the AHP waste is sterilized. After being shredded and going through an intermediate buffer to ensure a continuous process after the sterilization, the waste flow is further shredded and sent to the drying section where it is dried using dry warm air. The organic part which has been previously removed is condensed in a liquid phase, which is treated in a wastewater plant. The dry AHP waste is sent to a series of separators and to the final packaging phase from which the secondary raw materials exit in the form of flaked cellulose, SAP and shredded plastic with pieces smaller than 30 mm, after a final quality control using an optical reader.

2.3. Secondary Raw Materials applications

The new high-quality secondary raw materials can be transformed into high value applications, including also Fater closed loop applications for its own branded products (Fater is market leader in Italy in the production and commercialization of AHP products, with brands such as Pampers, Lines, Tampax and Lines Specialist). Many different applications have been already validated. The plastics are suitable for use in the main plastic processes; the cellulose can be used e.g. for absorbent products, high-quality paper, textiles and fertilizers, the super-absorbent polymer can be reintroduced to create new absorbent products and for use in the gardening sector.

3. Further developments through the EMBRACED project

The EMBRACED project further develops the technology into a first-of-its-kind multipurpose biorefinery, which allows the full recovery of AHP waste into high value bio-based and biodegradable products through the following main actions:

1. Cellulose from the AHP pre-treatment is converted through two different biotechnological processes into bio-based polyesters targeted at film applications and into bio-based PHB targeted at medical applications.
2. All the materials and by-products from the upstream (SAP, cellulose, plastic and wastewater) and downstream (PHB, bio-based polyesters and cells) are further processed towards the validation into products with increased sustainability, competitive cost and relevant market impacts.

4. Legislative drivers and barriers

A relevant driver for the implementation of AHP waste collection and recycling in Europe is the EU waste legal framework, as recently modified through the “Circular Economy Package”, through the binding targets set for municipal waste recycling and for reducing waste landfilling.

However, there is a very significant legislative barrier that still needs to be overcome: there is no commercialization potential without safe but widespread End-of-Waste (EoW) criteria for the AHP waste that specify when certain waste obtains a status of product (in Europe according to Art. 6 of the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC). The process is underway, to-date the Italian Minister of Environment has notified to the European Commission the Italian EoW decree, activating the TRIS procedure. Nevertheless, harmonized EoW criteria in Europe and Worldwide are essential for a widespread implementation of AHP waste recycling.

5. Conclusions

The FaterSMART recycling solution can divert worldwide up to 30,000,000 ton AHP waste yearly from landfilling and incineration, thus generating clear advantage for the environment, municipalities and citizens, the industry (waste management and chemical companies & secondary raw materials users) and creating new employment.

Acknowledgements

This work is carried out in the framework of the EMBRACED project that has received funding from the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 745746.

References

- [1] L. Upton, “Project Focus: Moving Europe’s mountain of nappies from landfill to helping create useful bio-based products”, *Biobased World Quarterly* #9, pp. 18-19, 2018.
- [2] “Nappies waste converted into high valuable material and products”, *FuturEnviro’s Magazine*, pp. 87-90, March 2018.
- [3] R. Bressa, “This is how we recycle nappies”, *Renewable Matter* N19, pp. 26-28, December 2017-January 2018.
- [4] A. Irwin, “Scientists want to use dirty nappies as a source of raw materials”, *Horizon Magazine*, October 8th, 2018: <https://horizon-magazine.eu/article/scientists-want-use-dirty-nappies-source-raw-materials.html>
- [5] FaterSMART website, <https://www.fatersmart.com/en/>
- [6] Embraced website, <https://www.embraced.eu/>